

Phase Coexistence and Structure of Coexisting phase in a New Perovskite Solid

Solution $x\text{Ba}(\text{Cu}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3-(1-x)\text{PbTiO}_3$

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Abstract

The motivation to replace the commercial high performance piezoelectric lead zirconate titanate (PZT) with a nontoxic substitute has led to a great surge in research interest in lead-free piezoelectric in the last decade [1]. In this context, it may be worth mentioning that a very large piezoelectric response is obtained when relaxor ferroelectrics $\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{Zn}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ are alloyed with ferroelectric PbTiO_3 . In this work, a new solid solution $x\text{Ba}(\text{Cu}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3-(1-x)\text{PbTiO}_3$ ($x=0.30, 0.35, 0.38, 0.40, 0.42$ and 0.45) ferroelectric ceramics were prepared using conventional solid state route and its formation was ascertained by X-ray diffraction method. Rietveld refined X-ray diffraction data of all the ceramics suggested the crystal structure change from tetragonal ($P4mm$) to cubic ($Pm3m$) symmetry with the increase in $\text{Ba}(\text{Cu}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ concentration (x). Average grain size is observed in the range of $1.5\sim 2.5\mu\text{m}$ for samples sintered at 1050°C for 2 hour. Variation of dielectric constant and dielectric loss with temperature show diffuse ferroelectric characteristics.

“Keywords: X-ray diffraction; Lead-free Piezoelectric; Dielectric; SEM”.

Reference:

1. Y. Saito, H. Takao, T. Tani, T. Nonoyama, K. Takatori, T. Homma, T. Nagaya, M. Nakamura; Nature **432** (2004) 84.